

FIRST GENERATION COLLEGE STUDENTS IN THE STUDY ABROAD COMMUNITY: THE
IMPORTANCE OF SUPPORTING UNDERREPRESENTED STUDENTS IN NAVIGATING
HIGHER EDUCATION

by

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Introduction

Higher education is marketed in a way that makes it seem limitless in opportunities and attainable for anyone with the desire to learn. Higher education research expert, Antigoni Papadimitriou (2015), states that universities increasingly need to compete with one another to seem more desirable to prospective students. University advertisements attempt to touch on a broad range of opportunities such as a diverse set of studies, career preparation and placement, the promise of feeling welcomed, and international programs in order to make themselves attractive to prospective students. Papadimitriou (2015) placed aspects of advertisements in different categories to explore different education abroad campaigns in Boston, New York, Oslo, Tokyo, and Toronto. These categories included: *Education*, “the different academic programs...the institution’s academic staff and the career preparation that they offer” (p.5); *Global Scope*, “international orientation”; *Research*, “included visual references to research” (p.7); and *Innovation*, “presented as the result of the education provided at a given institution” (p.8) . For example, the category *Education* included listing a wide range of majors/electives and advertising “Hands-on training.” The *Global Scope* category included phrases found in advertisements like “Challenge convention. Change our world.” and “Wherever you find yourself, [institution] is with you”. Advertisements within the *Innovation* and *Research* categories emphasized the institution’s ability to inspire societal advancement. Each of these institutions attempts to establish themselves as a place where education has the ability to transcend the classroom while also satisfying a wide variety of student talents and skill sets; they are feeding into the idealistic view of college. A study by business and marketing expert, Weng Marc Lim et al. (2020), suggests that universities differentiate themselves from others so that they can compete in a global education marketplace. It was found that the use of the marketing

mix: Prominence, Prospectus, Program, and Price had a significant and direct impact on the university's brand. Advertisements that implemented details of these four marketing techniques were more effective because they catered to students on a more personal and practical level (tuition flexibility, range of majors/electives, reputation of staff, personal emails, etc.). These forms of advertisements can seem very attractive, especially to nontraditional students since there is a blatant effort from universities to make these students feel welcomed, no matter their background. However, these university activities and programs, especially ones that cost money, are not always as accessible as they are advertised to be.

There are a variety of factors that inhibit students from taking advantage of programs and organizations such as major related clubs, intramural sports teams, career-oriented programs, and much more. For instance, someone's work schedule may only allow them to go to school at night which would make it difficult for them to engage with peers in their academic circle. In turn, they would be less exposed to major related activities that are put on and advertised by the university. A parent who is also a student may want to join a professional association on-campus to receive the "Hands-on training" that was advertised but cannot find care for their child during the meeting times. Someone who is low-income and a FGCS may want to study abroad and "Change our world" but has no knowledge of the programs they can apply to and scholarships/financial aid they can use. This is specifically the case for myself and many other students in my position. This is not to mention other factors that may inhibit FGCS from being able to view these international endeavors as tangible opportunities like finances, home life, work stability, travel anxiety, and lack of knowledge about university processes. Studying abroad was always something I desired to do but it felt unattainable for many reasons. It was not until I

was an orientation leader, who was immersed in the inner workings of university life, that I decided this was something I could do.

Now, paying for on-campus housing was *not* on the itinerary for my parents since they could not afford it. I was also supposed to save extra money from financial aid for after college, so this meant that paying for housing outside the country was not likely to happen. However, I was still determined to make this happen, but my family wrestled with supporting me in something they knew I have been wanting to do for a while and being realistic about our situation. There was an urgent family issue that would have been prolonged if I had studied abroad, so I had a hard choice to make. With the COVID-19 pandemic making its appearance not even a couple months after I got accepted into a program, my decision was made for me. Not only was the country on lockdown from the rest of the world but my family needed me and I could no longer go in good conscience. If I had not made the decision to quit my study abroad journey, I would have had to delay my graduation (which is something my parents are against) and my savings would have been put towards my own interests and not towards the interests of the family unit. This experience taught me a lot about how these “limitless opportunities” college offers, specifically for FGCS and other minority groups, are highly contingent upon the sacrifices their families are willing to make. Whether it is paying for their student’s expensive endeavors and memberships to join sororities/fraternities or having to cope with them being far away and displaced from the normal family dynamic, they are all relatively difficult situations for both parties involved. Major financial commitments make themselves tangible only when all factors and circumstances are perfectly aligned. When I began to save my leftover financial aid money, which I would have to use if I wanted to go abroad, I did not have enough in the first 2-3 years to do so. I would have had to wait for my 3rd year or 4th year, and even then, my entire

savings would be mostly, if not entirely, gone. There seems to be no room for FGCS to make missteps in their planning and organization of their study abroad venture which can seem very intimidating to someone who is already one emergency away from becoming financially unstable, being depended on by family, or unable to adjust to new places (like other countries) without adequate help. “Limitless opportunities” are based upon the idealistic and stereotypical college experiences presented in the media; having limitless opportunities is not a reality for many FGCS.

It is important to consider how a family’s beliefs about college can impact what activities their student involves themselves in, and it is also important to understand their perception of travel. I grew up with the idea that travel was done out of necessity or to visit family. I cannot recall a time when I traveled for leisure with my family because we could never afford to do so. Traveling abroad was something I understood to most likely happen when I became financially independent and had a job in my career field. When I proposed traveling abroad to study, my family’s main concern was the fact that I would be spending unnecessary amounts of money on travel for “no good reason”. The opinions that some of my family held about spending lots of money on this kind of experience was understandable because these trips did not make sense to them. My perception of travel was somewhat similar to theirs, but I dramatically changed my beliefs about this when I went to college. Travel became more personal to me in that I saw it as an opportunity for me to obtain a global perspective that I could apply in my future profession, experience/integrate into a new culture at a local level, adjust to a new academic life and routine, and help younger family members see themselves in this community. When I began college and learned more about studying abroad, I figured I would at least try to experience what felt like a distant and unfamiliar opportunity. Going abroad was also an experience I did not anticipate

doing alone since I always expected that I would be with either friends or family. If I were to get hurt or be in trouble while abroad, my family would have a difficult time trying to get to me since it would be expensive to do so. I was also scared to be alone in a country I had never been to before since my family was very close-knit and it would be very challenging to have to endure this kind of travel without their guidance or comfort. No matter the reason for hesitation, this speaks to a larger issue that FGCS face which is the feeling that they cannot access all aspects of university life. Universities should make a commitment to engage with their FGCS population and actively seek ways to integrate them into college life. This can be done through the implementation of FGCS based clubs, honors societies, trips, involvement and encouragement from faculty, and major/minor associations. These activities and outreach tactics will encourage FGCS to feel comfortable taking risks, and it will give them a foundation to build upon for future personal and professional engagements.

Literature Review

There has been a long standing tradition of the United States of encouraging college students to study abroad both formally and informally (Twombly, 2012). Studying abroad is an opportunity for students to engage with different cultures and learn a new language. The definition of study abroad has changed over the years, but I would argue that today's definition, used by the International Institute of Education (IIE) in their *Open Doors* report which was referenced by Professor Susan Twombly in *Study Abroad in a New Global Century: Renewing the Promise, Refining the Purpose*, does not capture the true potential of studying abroad. The IIE states that studying abroad is defined as "U.S. citizens and permanent residents who received academic credit at their U.S. home institution for study in another country" (IIE as cited in Twombly, 2012). I will not go in depth about this definition and why I think it is insufficient, but

I will give another example I feel suits the endeavor much better. The University of Wisconsin defines this opportunity as “all educational programs that take place outside the geographical boundaries of the United States” (University of Wisconsin as cited in Twombly, 2012). These definitions are U.S. centric, and, for the purposes of this project, this is how I will be defining “studying abroad” since I am specifically speaking about U.S.-based study abroad programming. More specifically, I will be discussing my personal experiences and other’s experiences in the study abroad community at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) and at CSUF.

For centuries, study abroad programs have been a way for people to travel abroad/become culturally competent, and the beginning of the 20th century marked the implementation of “for-credit” programs (Twombly, 2012). Those who have studied abroad have been mostly white, female, young, financially comfortable, and majored in fine arts and humanities (Twombly, 2012). The first two types of study abroad programs were Junior Year Abroad (JYA) and faculty led programs. The intention behind these programs was to learn new languages, about different cultures (sometimes in order to prevent war), and to develop academically (Twombly, 2012). It was surprising to find out that studying abroad was a political gesture in many instances, but it makes sense when thinking about the influences of war on the societal beliefs about studying abroad. For example, WW1, WW2, the Vietnam and Korean War, the Cold War, and 9/11 have influenced this community through legislation and types of opportunities offered. Some of the policies and organizations established after WW2 to encourage studying abroad include the Fulbright International Education Exchange Program, which allowed students to receive grants to teach English abroad; the Council On International Educational Exchange (CIEE), which provided study abroad opportunities for students and professionals; and the National Association of Foreign Student Affairs (NAFSA), which is

dedicated to international education and policy making (Twombly, 2012). The encouragement of studying abroad increased after the Vietnam, Korean, and Cold Wars. Each of these wars greatly emphasized a need for peace and diplomacy which changed the intention behind studying abroad. The IIE stated that the world could not “achieve lasting peace without greater understanding between nations” (IIE as cited in Twombly, 2012). Students and faculty were often used as pawns by the government to “Americanize” others and fight the Communist regimes, and post-9/11 signified another shift in the study abroad community as international tensions rose once more. There was a desperate call by the American Council on Education (ACE) to prioritize international education in order to benefit the nation and to avoid more conflict (Twombly, 2012).

There are different types of programs that students and faculty can participate in. There are institutionally administered programs, foreign institutes, and third-party providers (Twombly, 2012). All these programs are valid study abroad options, however, there is something to be said about their accessibility. There is a historic underrepresentation of racial and ethnic minorities, science and math majors, students with disabilities, students with low socioeconomic status (SES), and men (Twombly, 2012). The decision to enter the study abroad community is a major one, and the amount of effort it takes to fully understand the process can further our understanding about educational opportunities and accessibility in higher education. There are plenty of factors that contribute to one’s ability and desire to study abroad which include: human, economic, social, and cultural capital. Each of these factors provides understanding of students and their situations as it pertains to their knowledge of the benefits of studying abroad, financial status, information that can help them access studying abroad, and their attitudes towards improving cultural competence (Twombly, 2012). It is impossible to fully grasp and mend these

disparities if there is no effort to understand their nuances. Even then, there would have to be extra consideration for other important factors that contribute to this decision such as major, professional goals, and desired graduation time.

The factor that I am interested in specifically is FGCS status which typically intersects with low-SES and other marginalized identities. In 2019/2020, 70% of study abroad students were White, 10.6% were Latino(a), 8.6% were Asian or Pacific Islander, 5.5% were Black or African American, 4.8% were Multiracial, and 0.5% were Native American or Alaska Native (Open Doors Report, 2021). The National Center for Education Statistics (2017) found that 76% of FGCS who enroll in college do so at public institutions. This is paired with the fact that 52% of those students enroll at public two-year institutions, and only 6% of FGCS enroll in highly selective four-year institutions. This may be because they are too expensive and or far away, but it is unfortunate because a more rigorous environment may be more beneficial for these students. Higher education expert and reporter for the Brookings Institution, Johnathan Rothwell wrote in his 2015 report on *The Stubborn Race and Class Gaps in College Quality*, that Black/African American, Hispanic, and low-income students had the lowest graduation rates, earnings after attendance, and the highest default rate on federal student loans. The Pell Institute's 2021 Report on indicators of higher education equity found that dependent students who enrolled in college in 2011-12 and who were both low income and FGCS were found to have a 21% chance of graduating with a 4-year degree in 6 years. This is compared to the 66% chance that CGCS and non-low-income students have in completing their 4-year degree in 6 years. As for financial status, the Pew Research Center (2021) uncovered that households headed by FGCS (aged 22-59) had a median adjusted household income of \$65,200 in 2019 compared to their CGCS counterparts who earned \$100,900. These statistics are not surprising; however, they do not

represent those who did not apply for financial aid either because they didn't understand the process or because they didn't know about that option. Low-SES is one of the many factors that contribute to the lack of informational resources that FGCS have when entering college (Brown, 2016). With that being said, the lack of FGCS representation in the study abroad community is expected.

Underrepresented CSUF Experiences in Study Abroad

My interactions with FGCS are limited to those I happen to meet in passing, and it has been more difficult to establish such connections with the COVID-19 pandemic limiting social interactions and in-person classes for the past two years. However, I decided that I should make an effort to meet other students like myself who represent the FGCS community at CSUF. I set out to find FGCS who had applied/been accepted to go abroad through CSUF or had studied abroad before. I drafted an email with our Study Abroad Office with the help of Aileen Vickory, one of our amazing Study Abroad Advisors. She sent out a mass email about my project to all study abroad students who applied to study abroad, studied abroad or who are currently doing so, and those who are yet to go on their big adventure. I have never interviewed people previously, let alone about personal topics like this, so I was very nervous going into it. To say the least, these conversations were very fulfilling and we all shared many of the same experiences with/perceptions of travel and higher education.

Identities, Level of Parent Education, and Association with Study Abroad and Global Engagement (SAGE)

Anastasia, the first person I interviewed, is a wife, mother, and student who is in her 40s. She is studying in a program for extended education and is getting a BA in Humanities and

Social Sciences. Her course is completely online, and she is currently taking 2 classes per semester which will result in her graduating in Spring of 2024. She initially graduated high school in 1994 and went to CSUF to study business for a couple of semesters before she became burnt out and soon pregnant with her first child. When her son was one year old, she began taking classes again at a community college, eventually earning an AA in liberal arts. Over the years and while taking these classes, she had her second son, got remarried, and began a business with her husband. Neither of her parents went to college and wanted her and her sister to obtain a Bachelor's degree. She grew up in a low-income household which made Anastasia's FGCS experience now as an older adult more freeing since she is financially independent and stable. She is currently registered to go on a month-long trip to Bali this June.

Brandon, a 2nd year Master's student studying computer science, is graduating this semester and will soon be working for Microsoft. He first attended college at UC Santa Cruz in 2012 and got his Bachelor's in 2017. Neither of his parents attended college and they did not have an in-depth understanding about it. Brandon is also a first-generation immigrant whose parents were born in Mexico, and he is the first person in his family to have studied abroad. In 2016, he submitted a leave of absence from UC Santa Cruz and spent a semester at University of the Philippines, Dilman (UP Dilman). When he enrolled at CSUF, he applied to go to South Korea for a semester, but the COVID-19 Pandemic kept suspending his trip. With graduation coming up, he decided to no longer pursue his trip this Fall 2022 semester.

One of the two freshmen I interviewed was Lily, who graduated high school in 2021 and is a linguistics major; she is a full-time student working a part-time job. She comes from a low-income family, her parents are immigrants from China, and neither of them attended college. Lily was able to study abroad in Shanghai during high school with the Council On International

Educational Exchange (CIEE). Now that she is at CSUF, she wants to study abroad in Mexico for the Fall 2022 semester.

Katrina was the other freshman I interviewed, and she also graduated high school in 2021 like Lily. Katrina is an art major who desires to do freelance work in graphic design, and she has many different visions she hopes to execute during her time at CSUF. She comes from a low-income family and is a first-generation immigrant whose parents came from Mexico and did not attend college. She is currently involved with SAGE's Village Book Builders and is a Global Titan Ambassador (GTA). Village Book Builders is an organization that focuses on the educational disparities in the global south through mentoring programs and building libraries. She is planning on studying abroad in the future and is open to any trips offered.

Josie, a second-year business administration and marketing student, is a part-time barista and someone who wants to bring communities together by working with other creatives in the graphic design industry. She is a first-generation Asian-American immigrant whose parents moved here when they were very young. Her father graduated from a 4-year university in Texas and her mother had some college experience at California State University, Long Beach but did not finish her time there. Josie is currently registered to go to South Korea for the Fall 2022 semester.

Avery is a senior President's Scholar and political science major whose parents grew up and went to college in Mexico. Their degrees did not transfer to the U.S. because their education is considered community college level. She is unsure of what she wants to do after graduation this May but is very open to new experiences, and she describes herself as a "go with the flow" type of person. She was able to take a two-week trip to Poland in the summer during her

sophomore year at CSUF. She was inspired to study abroad again and applied to go to France for a semester, but the COVID-19 pandemic suspended this trip and she decided not to go.

Tricia is a 5th year psychology major who is double minoring in both music and marketing. She is a first-generation immigrant whose parents are from Mexico. She describes her family as being low-income, and she is the first in her family to be graduating from college. Her hopes for her post-graduate life after this May include possibly teaching abroad as well as marketing and making social media content for travel organizations. She is set to study abroad in South Korea Fall 2022 semester after turning down a study abroad trip to Denmark a couple years ago so she could work and save money.

Together, these students represent some of the diversity that is within the FGCS community. Each of these students have had limited travel experience in their upbringing that influenced their decision to involve themselves in the SAGE community. Studying abroad, or preparing and anticipating to do so, has opened their eyes to a new set of possibilities. During these interviews, I was able to uncover both universal and unique experiences that warrant a discussion. While talking to these students, I decided not to solely focus on the discourses or perceptions that travel is a “privilege” or “luxury,” I focus instead on the nuanced experiences of FGCS, their families, and their path to personal and academic success. There are, however, discussions about how travel was not accessible to them due to finances and or other circumstances. It is necessary to note that these circumstances were not in the control of them or their family and should not be used to justify their underrepresentation in the study abroad community. It is also important to me and to these students that their stories are not used to take pity on them. Rather, it is my hope that the reader takes this opportunity to grasp just how motivated, curious, and proud these First-Generation College Students are.

FGCS and Parents: Education, Studying Abroad, Considerations

When contemplating whether to study abroad, there are a number of factors that contribute to the decision. For the FGCS I talked to, there were a lot of concerns around finances, graduation delays, and traveling. Anastasia, who is a business owner, has children, and is married, had plenty to consider when planning her trip abroad. She knew that she did not want to go for long and said, “This is a nice little side trip and doesn’t cost me too much time.” During our discussions, it was apparent to me that she had way less restrictions now compared to when she began college. She mentioned how she had to go to a local university because she could not afford to go far and had to support herself through college; her parents also expected her to graduate in four years. The reality of these circumstances is that they do not allow for much exploration, especially through the means of studying abroad. I wanted to encourage her to study abroad for a whole semester or year like she said she wanted to when she first began college, but I realized that her wants had changed. I associate a longer time abroad with being the most “worth it”, but that is because I am a very young college student with less responsibilities than a wife, business owner, and mother. She is content with where her life is and is just happy to be able to have this kind of experience now that she is able to do so with little worry or concern. There is no use in dwelling on what she could have done earlier on if her circumstances were different because that would imply regret, and she gave me no sign of regretting any decision she made that got her to where she is today. She also values community which means that being away from her cohort for too long would be difficult. She admitted to wanting to maximize her time with her peers since these people are with her from beginning to end, and as a FGCS, a tight college community means everything. She stated that she wants to “get the degree and be done” so that she can accomplish this lifegoal she set for herself. It is important to stress that this is for

herself and for nothing else; she does not need this degree for the same reasons I need mine, which is to get a good paying job. Her college experience is under her control and within her own boundaries which is a lot more than I can say for myself. While talking to Anastasia, I realized that this one-month trip is equivalent to my (almost) semester abroad. Her time abroad will be as eye-opening and unforgettable as mine would have been, and I could not be more excited for her.

Every FGCS I talked to decided to choose a short-term study abroad program, which Kyle Rausch, Executive Director of Arizona State University's Study Abroad Office, states that these programs in particular are attractive to FGCS and make studying abroad more accessible (Rausch, 2017). For Anastasia, she chose a short-term program because it allowed her to remain involved with her cohort/program, her family, and her business. For students like Lily, it was because short-term programs are less risky when it comes to transferring classes over to the home university, ensuring that graduation is not delayed. Now, Lily's parents did not place the expectation of graduating in four years on her, she did. She had two main reasons for this sense of urgency: she does not want to delay her career, she wants to make good money as soon as possible, and she does not want to risk getting less financial aid during those additional years. A short-term program was perfect for her, almost meant to be. Her parents encouraged her to take a year abroad, but she said, "No no no, I thought about it. I was the one ruminating the pros and cons of the full academic year versus just the semester." For FGCS who are using state and federal aid to put themselves through college, prolonging graduation is not ideal because there is a limit on how long they provide funding. Lily, and I, have noticed that every time we apply for the Free Application for Federal Student Aid (FAFSA), our expected family contribution (EFC) increases and we get less money. Using financial aid is crucial to our, and other low-income

students, being able to attend college. Graduating in four years ensures that we will be able to pay for college with little to no debt. In contrast to Lily, Avery's parents want her to graduate in four years. Because of this expectation, she was weary about taking too many classes abroad since there was a possibility that they would not transfer. Avery was also a little more concerned about finances than Lily since she lives paycheck to paycheck and living abroad for an extended period of time would jeopardize her income and push her to take out loans, something she was adamant about not doing. This is why her two-week trip to Poland worked out so well and why her semester long trip to France would have required a lot more financial preparation. Avery stressed the fact that parents of FGCS do not know the difficult processes involved in obtaining a degree and a high paying job but are adamant about us getting to that point. When it comes to being excited about new opportunities, Avery's and Lily's parents are always on board, but they are not as in the know about how they get there. There is an inherent trust that parents of FGCS have in their children when it comes to conducting their college experience. Each of their parents were okay with them studying abroad because they figured that they had the money saved up from financial aid, work, and scholarships as well as knowledge about the details of the trip. If this were not the case, they would have been less supportive. This was also true for myself and my parents as they were always very proud and supportive, but there is a small disconnect when it comes to explaining my collegiate career to them and they just trust that I know what is best for me. It is also important to clarify that just because parents of FGCS do not have extensive knowledge on collegiate level programs does not mean they are not willing to help their student. Many of the students I talked to said that their parents, when they got on board with them studying abroad, were helpful in any way they could be.

Getting parents and guardians of FGCS to support their study abroad ventures is a varying experience among this population. Some students I talked to had little to no push back and their families were immediately okay with them going abroad. Others, like Josie, had to introduce this idea very early on. Her parents, as she grew up, provided all they could for her. They aimed, and continue to aim, to take care of her as much as they can so that she did not have to worry about much. Josie recalls having to beg her parents to let her get a job in high school because they were confused about why she needed an income when she had them, despite her family being low-income. When she told her parents that she applied for a job, her mother jokingly said that she hoped she did not get it. Eventually, they ended up being happy for her and supported her decision to be somewhat financially independent. She has wanted to study abroad for a while now, and she knew she had to mention it to her parents as soon as possible. Initially, they were against her studying abroad because it made them feel like she was going to be completely cut off from them. This countered their desire to provide for her and keep her safe from the outside world for as long as they could, and Josie contributed this way of thinking to her Asian-American first-generation immigrant status. With her limited travel experience including only seeing family for a couple of days a year, her parents' concern is no surprise and almost expected. Josie sees a lot of similarities between her and her parents as far as their Asian-American experience since they were very young when they moved to the U.S. She said that she told her parents that, "My Asian-American experience is different from yours, and I am in the generation where people want to go places, people want to do things. People don't want to be the norm anymore, and I kind of resonate with that a lot." Convincing them to allow her to go to South Korea for a semester took many serious conversations and a lot of adjusting. However, they did not want her to resent them for not letting her go and are gradually understanding her

need for independence as time goes on. All of the FGCS I talked to, including myself, resonate with the fact that our parents just want us to have a better life than they had at our age. Taking risks like studying abroad, where a lot can go wrong financially, physically, and emotionally, is something that our parents had to warm up to because it is not necessarily “on the beaten path”. I believe that our differing generations, as Josie alluded to, are a major contributor to the differences between us and our parents. Their perception of what college is like is different from ours for the simple fact that we are experiencing it and they did not, or at least not in the ways that we are. Studying abroad is not necessary to get a degree or a good paying job that sets you up for life, it is viewed as a luxury. However, it is a major asset to those who get to participate since it is an experience that is valued in the workforce (Institute of International Education, 2017). A great example of a parent’s worst fear coming true is when the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 came about. Many students were abroad when the pandemic was announced, and they were stuck in different countries and were completely displaced from their families during uncertain times. These fears are not without proper reason, and it is up to FGCS to be patient with their loved ones as they also try and do what is best for themselves.

Travel Experiences and Motivations to Travel

All participants admitted that, growing up, they only traveled for the purpose of seeing family and that their experiences with travel were very limited. Brandon talked about how he came from a poor family and how his parents were undocumented immigrants. His parents were not well acquainted with traveling, and they viewed travel as more of a necessity to achieve better opportunities. Growing up, he had to spend a lot of time at home to avoid raising suspicions about his parents’ citizenship and he described it as a “caged kind of experience”. He also spent some time living in Mexico with his grandmother because his mother had to save

money in the U.S. In Mexico, he recalls seeing a variety of situations that he says would not encourage anyone to explore. Despite travel not always being a part of his plan, the fact that it was not was one of his motivations to do so. He got very used to being indoors, but once he got into college, he met people who had a very different experience. They had wonderful tales from their trips either studying abroad or traveling with family and friends for fun. This sparked a sort of “rage”, as Brandon describes it, and he began to think, “Why couldn’t I experience this?”.

Tricia had a similar experience in that she also questioned why she couldn’t travel around a lot growing up. Her parents introduced the idea at a young age, much like mine had, that traveling was for the rich and wealthy. She would visit her grandparents in Mexico, help them with anything they needed, spend quality time with them, and then go home. These trips were meaningful to Tricia despite how “It never felt like vacation, it felt like duty.”, but this encouraged her to want to travel for herself. She stated that she wanted to prove the mentality that travel was for the rich and wealthy wrong. It is important to her that she breaks the generational barriers and roadblocks that she was presented with her whole life so that she can encourage those around her to do the same. This is why she is going to take a trip to Cancún with her sister this September, and she is very excited about it. In comparison to Brandon and Tricia, Avery experienced a similar “go-getter” mentality. Her traveling was restricted to seeing family and her parents did not take much time off work because they needed the income. However, traveling was always something she wanted to do. Since her study abroad trip to France was suspended because of COVID-19, she decided to move up to Seattle with her partner and stay there for a semester instead. With school and her job online, she was able to study outside of her place of comfort and still have an income. Since the pandemic hindered their ability to go out and explore extensively, they found small ways to satisfy their curiosity. She doesn’t see

traveling as something that needs to be filled with events and luxuries, rather, specifically while living in Seattle, she was content with a walk around the block.

During these three conversations, something was made incredibly apparent: FGCS may not have an extensive amount of social capital with regards to college, but they have plenty of motivation to take advantage of resources they come across or are provided with by others. Despite having past experiences that obstructed their view of traveling, the desire to travel found its way into their lives. This would mean that, when they have proper resources and guidance, FGCS would pursue a variety of ventures just as any CGCS would. I was raised with the same sentiment as Tricia: “travel is for the wealthy”, and I always believed that when I finally got to travel for myself, it would be when I was much older and financially independent. It was not until I was blatantly exposed to the study abroad office as an Orientation Leader that I decided and realized that studying abroad was something I could do. At that point, I was open to any kind of experience and willing to figure out the details because I was beginning to feel confident enough to explore different options. Brandon agreed with the notion that FGCS, more so than CGCS, need extra guidance from faculty in order to build confidence and comfortability when treading unfamiliar waters.

Their lack of comfortability can be minimized by genuine and intentional exposure to faculty through either personal outreach or other methods of resource sharing so that students who are less comfortable can become more comfortable. Micol Hutchison, Director of Program Development and Student Success in University College at Virginia Commonwealth University, conducted a study in 2017 where he and his colleagues interviewed both FGCS and CGCS in order to understand their perceptions of faculty (Hutchison, 2017). It was demonstrated that FGCS in the Summer Scholars program felt more confident about initiating professional

relationships with faculty. The key component of this program was that it had professors who were specifically passionate about student involvement. Hutchison (2017) found that FGCS were less likely to feel comfortable around faculty which, in my experience, inevitably leads to these students not taking advantage of all the resources available to them. A great example from my interviews that exemplified this phenomenon was when I was talking to Tricia about her sophomore year. At that time, she was not doing as well as she usually did (more on that later), so one of her professors reached out to her about her drastic grade drop. This professor was very understanding, compassionate, and dedicated to making sure that Tricia felt like she belonged at CSUF. This is when she made her comeback and began to do very well in her classes once more. Funny enough, this same professor was the one who encouraged her to study abroad in Denmark and who wrote her a letter of recommendation for it. Unfortunately, as mentioned previously, Tricia did not go on this trip, but the principle remains: positive faculty involvement inspired student involvement and motivation.

Faculty Interactions and Relationships

An added, and important, layer to this discussion lies in the lack of information that FGCS have with regards to studying abroad. How can someone study abroad if they do not view it as a feasible opportunity in the first place? Having parental guidance when trying to navigate collegiate spaces makes committing to activities like studying abroad much more accessible. This is not the same experience for students whose parents did not attend or finish college since they only know as much or less about college than their student. In my own experience, my mother and father did not even consider that I would want to study abroad when trying to prepare me for college. Their main focus was getting me to understand the importance of college which, to them, was the amount of wealth I would accumulate with my degree. More emphasis was

placed on getting good grades rather than spending time and money on activities and clubs. They were not against me pursuing fun activities or clubs as they encouraged my participation, but it was only discussed when I brought it up. As I mentioned before, I did not consider seriously studying abroad until I became an Orientation Leader and was incentivized to invest time in getting to know CSUF. What I enjoyed about this experience the most was how the faculty, staff, and students involved with the orientation process made it a point to advertise to Orientation Leaders as well. There were frequent conversations about scholarships, financial aid, and campus organizations dedicated to making college seem less intimidating. This is when I realized the importance of faculty involvement in facilitating a student's interest and desire to be involved in university activities.

Students' motivations and ventures are best supported when the university and its staff support them directly. Many students utilize faculty support in order to conduct important business such as club events, job applications, and to gain insight about their desired profession. However, if students are not comfortable with expressing their questions, concerns, or goals with faculty, they may miss out on some of the essential development and critical information needed to be successful in their field. The previously mentioned study by Hutchison (2017) took place at the university during the summer before the participants' first semester in college. This study assessed the experiences of the students with Bourdieuan concepts: field (the university in this instance), habitus (self-perception and disposition), cultural capital (essential skills and information), and social capital (ability to access a network). The students were Non-FGCS (CGCS) and FGCS who were voluntarily a part of the Summer Scholars program which allowed them to live on campus and take classes for credit. About 36 students were given a survey to provide demographic information. There were about 16 students who were selected to be

individually interviewed for phase 2. In phase 3, there were 8 self-selected students who participated in the focus groups. As I read through the interviews, it was clear to me that CGCS had a much easier time talking to and getting to know faculty members. For instance, Rose, who is CGCS, states that she sees professors as people first, not superiors (p.15). Another student who is CGCS, Cassie, emails her professors frequently to get information and to talk about life (p.16). These kinds of interactions were very different from the interactions FGCS had with faculty members. Students Mary Lou, Jessica, and Emma, who were all FGCS expressed more doubt about forming a professional and personal relationship with their professors (Hutchison, 2017). Their initial impressions of faculty members showed that they were intimidated by them and did not view them as equals. Some of their perceptions included feeling as if their professors were “super mean” or did “not want to be bothered” (p.21). Some FGCS even believed that becoming close to a professor would be viewed as creepy. The study found that the most common quality linked to FGCS perceptions of faculty was unfamiliarity. In contrast with CGCS, FGCS did not have a great understanding of student-professor relationships and that impacted their ability to form meaningful connections with them. There were major differences found between the perceptions FGCS had the first semester and their perceptions in their second semester. This was especially true for Mary Lou, who credited the summer program that enabled her to attain a work-study job in which she was able to interact with faculty frequently and become more comfortable with them. Stephanie and Emma followed a similar pattern in that as they got more familiar with their professors and university, they began to believe that professors truly care about their students. These students more closely resembled CGCS in their perceptions of faculty during the second semester. This demonstrates that when students are unfamiliar with a certain field it is likely that their habitus does not fit the habitus of the university field. It was found that

as FGCS become more familiar with university, they gain cultural and social capital which allows them to feel more comfortable interacting with university faculty and activities. This highlights the importance of faculty involvement in the professional and social development of their FGCS population.

The initial perceptions of faculty as shown in this study by FGCS would not have given them the ability or confidence to reach out to professors and faculty members as quickly. With the help of the Summer Scholar's program, these students were able to engage in a discussion about their concerns and misconceptions about faculty. When I was an orientation leader, we got to conduct fulfilling, but uncomfortable, conversations with a select few students who came from marginalized backgrounds (this included FGCS) about their concerns heading into college. It was an overnight workshop where the students got to stay in the dorms and meet their peers. After this conversation, I noticed that they felt a little better about beginning college and spoke about this new chapter in a positive manner. If it were not for the efforts of the CSUF faculty, this would have never been able to happen and these students would have begun their first semester, possibly, without ever having their concerns and experiences listened to. These discussions should be routine when universities are welcoming incoming students to ensure that students are receiving the unique support they require.

Literature that pays special attention to the differences between FGCS and CGCS warrants further conversation about how important it is to address the impact that faculty members have on students, especially FGCS. For those I interviewed, there were stories that made me hopeful and others that made me disheartened. There are plenty of factors that contribute to a student's perception of faculty, and for me and these students, this perception was heavily influenced by how they welcomed their students. When entering college, I had the

expectation that all faculty would make the same effort that my previous teachers made in K-12 to ensure my educational development. This is not the case. Professors have far more students to consider and less class time than any high school teacher which contributes to the lack of personal engagement I have noticed. FGCS, as previously mentioned, already have a difficult time compared to their CGCS counterparts when interacting with faculty. Therefore, having positive and motivating relationships with university faculty is necessary for facilitating a successful educational experience for all.

The students I talked to admitted that their interactions with CSUF and higher education faculty impacted their college experience. Anastasia, being an older student, felt confident when talking to faculty and she was able to do so with little trouble. This is because she is more mature now and is also a professional in her own right since she owns and runs a business. When it came time to ask her program director about whether or not she would be able to commit to her trip to Bali, she did not hesitate once. Hearing this experience was mind-blowing to me because when I had to go through a similar process with my department, I was very nervous to do so. Her life experience, age, and occupation influence how she interacts with faculty more so than her FGCS status which makes sense since she is on a similar playing field as her professors. This is not the case for the majority of FGCS I talked to since they are younger and therefore have less life experience and are likely to have less professional experience.

Some of the FGCS disclosed personal information about themselves and their families that impacted their academic career to faculty, and they were denied the proper support and resources that they needed to feel better about their situation. Tricia remembers two very distinct experiences with faculty her sophomore year that impacted her college experience in a negative way. These two faculty members made comments that alluded to the idea that “people like her”

(referring to her low-income and FGCS status) do not understand what is needed to be successful and that she did not know how the real world worked. These comments stuck with her, and they contributed to her academic struggles during that year; she stopped going to classes and stopped taking exams which resulted in her failing two classes and being on academic probation. One of her professors noticed Tricia struggling and reached out to help her get back on track. With this professor's encouragement and Tricia's inherent desire to do well in school, she aced the majority of her classes her junior year (a total of 18 units per semester) and increased her grade point average (GPA). During this transition, she kept telling herself that she would not allow the words of others to get to her and her FGCS/low-income status to define her. This professor became a sort of mentor and helped Tricia see herself as the competent and professional individual she always was and as someone who was capable of pursuing any venture she desired, like studying abroad. Without intervention from a faculty member, it would be difficult to say whether or not Tricia would have met the requirements (GPA, grades, funds, information, etc.) to study abroad in South Korea in Fall 2021. This is not to say that Tricia would have continued to do poorly in school, but it is to say that faculty involvement was a great asset that allowed her to continue to go above and beyond. Tricia benefitted greatly from this relationship, and it showed her that she was capable of pursuing so much more than she initially believed. Avery had a similar experience when she applied for the trip to Poland. She stopped filling out her application because she became unmotivated and knew it was too expensive for her, but when one faculty member reached out about the unfinished application, everything changed. This faculty member provided her with scholarships and resources to ensure that she knew all of the financing options, and she admits that without the follow-up, she would have never gone on that trip. It is no question that FGCS are open to experience and accepting of new opportunities, they just needed

the extra guidance and encouragement. The effort and compassion shown by these two faculty members should be the standard that all higher education faculty are held to because it is obvious that the students, especially FGCS, are willing to accept their involvement.

Josie, similar to Tricia, experienced a situation where a professor lacked compassionate care to a very sensitive situation she was going through. Her step-father had to go to rehab for alcohol abuse for the 3rd time that year, and no adults were home to watch the younger children. This professor refused to work with Josie when she asked for leniency and empathy during this difficult time when she was unsure if she would be able to go to class or turn in assignments. Low-income individuals are at greater risk of participating in heavy drinking and thus alcohol abuse (Cerdá, 2012). This is an issue that disproportionately affects low-income households, and the lack of accommodation she received is outrageous. There is a systemic lack of support from governments across the world when it comes to aiding low-income and poverty stricken families in obtaining access to education and basic needs, as stated by Komala Ramachandra, Senior Researcher in the Business and Human Rights division of Human Rights Watch, in her article, “Breaking the Poverty Trap: Why Poverty and Inequality are Human Rights Issues” (Ramachandra, 2020). Seeing higher education institutions embody that same lack of support and care is not surprising, but it is something that needs to be addressed. Josie believes that, “This is something that needs to be taken into account. People need to know this stuff. I feel like whatever is happening to me is happening to other people”. She also states that she does not, “know why we need to be reprimanded for something out of our control”, which is a very valid point. Poverty stricken and low-income individuals face are not always controllable and are simply products of that kind of environment. Understanding the individuals who are likely to be FGCS is imperative if we are to address issues that these students face. Yes, Josie is a student

who has committed to an education, but that does not mean she is not still a low-income student with a family that is dealing with issues low-income households disproportionately face. We cannot dismiss the importance of intersectionality during these conversations, and higher education institutions need to make a blatant effort to ensure that their faculty are sensitive to their students.

Insensitivity from faculty, as stated by these students, does not encourage student involvement and it negatively impacts their perceptions of higher education. Both Tricia and Josie admit that they did not feel like the environment facilitated by those unsupportive faculty members was a good foundation to inspire student involvement and motivation. This was especially the case for Katrina, who was involved in an academic organization on campus and did not feel like she was treated in a welcoming manner. This program did not demonstrate behaviors that showed they wanted to work with her demanding academic schedule which caused her to feel unheard and dismissed. She spent about a week stressed and anxious over this situation because she wanted to be involved in this program. There is an obvious difference between the outcomes when students have a positive experience with faculty versus when they do not. This kind of difference matters to students, especially FGCS who need more help when navigating higher education. Microaggressions and unproductive ways of expressing frustration is not what faculty should respond with when they see their students struggling.

FGCS Specific Programing in Higher Education

These kinds of situations speak to a larger conversation about faculty outreach and involvement in the lives of FGCS. If higher education institutions want to ensure that their FGCS population thrives on their campus, there needs to be active effort in giving them proper aid. This means that implementing FGCS specific programs and outreach that aim to acknowledge the

concerns and identities of FGCS should be taken into account. There are plenty of references that higher education institutions can use such as the Benjamin A. Gilman Scholarship, the International Studies Abroad (ISA) and Arizona State University's (ASU) Planning Scholars Program, and University of California's (USC) Norman Topping Scholars Program (NTSP). This is not an exhaustive list of FGCS and underrepresented minority specific programs that U.S. universities have, but these are some that caught my attention.

Currently, I am a Gilman Scholarship recipient, and I do feel like this program deserves a lot more recognition than it is given. This program was created in 2000 and aims to provide students who are Pell Grant recipients with financial stability during their time abroad. The scholarships vary, but students can earn up to five thousand dollars to put towards their abroad program whether it be at a university or internship site. I used my scholarship for a virtual internship in Valencia, Spain and it has served me well. It should be noted that Gilman's involvement in virtual programs is because of the COVID-19 pandemic and is anticipated to end on April 30, 2023. Upon finishing the chosen abroad program, students are required to complete the Follow-On Service project within six months of completion. This project's goal is to increase awareness of study abroad opportunities as well as the Gilman Scholarship. The Follow-On Service project allows for students to invest time in reflecting on their experience abroad so that they can appreciate it even more. Being that studying abroad is typically viewed as a once in a lifetime opportunity for FGCS, this is a wonderful way to encourage them to become involved and integrated in the communities they are placed in so that they will take full advantage. I can say with immense confidence that this scholarship enabled me to feel more prepared in pursuing my study abroad venture, especially when I was still planning on studying in Wales. My financial needs were mostly taken care of and I am able to invest time in creating a project to

promote this scholarship to other students like myself. It has been mentioned to me by a CSUF Honors Program faculty member that this program is not well known to CSUF students. This is unfortunate because I believe that this scholarship can have a major impact on student involvement in CSUF's study abroad community. The students I talked to agree that finances are one of the main deciding factors when considering studying abroad, so it would serve FGCS well if more information about financing study abroad was readily available and widely advertised.

The Gilman Scholarship provides students with reassurance that their study abroad venture, no matter where it takes them, will center the experience and not their hesitations or doubts. The ISA's and ASU's Planning Scholars Scholarship Program also provides this security for participating students. Kyle Rausch, now Executive Director of Study Abroad at University of Illinois Chicago, references this program in his dissertation, *First Generation Strength: Supporting First-Generation College Students in Study Abroad* (Rausch, 2017). In this study it was found that the Planning Scholars Scholarship Program (PSSP), a program for FGCS who want to pursue study abroad, increased the students' confidence in their study abroad venture. It was noted that FGCS had concerns about finances, finding a program that would enable them to graduate at their preferred time, making friends abroad, and traveling alone (Rausch, 2017). These concerns are almost identical to those that were mentioned in the interviews I conducted which supports the idea that there are universal struggles experienced by FGCS. Knowing these universal struggles and identifying common and unique experiences that FGCS have is important when implementing programs to help aid these students in higher education; this is why the PSSP was able to make the impact that it did. Successful programs should have a similar outcome as the PSSP: confident first-generation college students who are adequately prepared to become global citizens.

Another great program that can be used as a reference when looking to implement FGCS specific programming is the Norman Toppings Scholars Program. The NTSP identifies students who are low-income and who have overcome major obstacles in order to enter the world of higher education. Students in this program have the opportunity to travel abroad with one of the coordinators, George J. Sanchez, Professor and Director of Dornsife at USC, who was inspired by the fact that FGCS at USC were the least likely population to study abroad (Sanchez, 2012). Students participate in a three and a half week “Maymester” course that takes place after commencement and before the summer semester. This course is applied to their spring course load, takes full advantage of their financial aid packages, and provides financial support for their travels through the Norman Topping Program. Students in this program participate in a faculty-led trip to Japan for about two weeks; the week leading up to this trip is used to learn about Japanese culture in Los Angeles. Other study abroad programs are not typically structured in a way that caters FGCS concerns and doubts (finances, traveling abroad on their own, going on a plane for the first time, etc.), but the faculty involved make sure that these issues are addressed during the weeks leading up to the trip. Like the Gilman Scholarship, this program also seeks to teach students how to integrate what they learned abroad into a project. This project requires students to focus on their major/intellectual interests in the context of Japanese society. Projects like this enable students to expand their knowledge about their major and career path in a way that integrates a global perspective and thus a more informed understanding of what they want to pursue. This project has also inspired some students involved to pursue career options they did not previously think about (Sanchez, 2012).

When higher education institutions invest time in creating study abroad programs that center underrepresented students and include faculty who are passionate about FGCS success,

there are positive academic, social, and career outcomes. These outcomes include changes in career paths due to studying abroad, connections with faculty, professional development, and increased academic motivation (Sanchez, 2012; Rausch, 2017). I want to stress the importance of including faculty who are dedicated to diversifying programs on their respective campuses. Not only is it important to advertise programs like those above to encourage participation in the study abroad community, it is also important to ensure that these programs are staffed with people who have a passion for enabling student success no matter their background. These faculty should also have similar experiences to these students such as being a first-generation immigrant, racial/ethnic minority, FGCS, having been low-income, etc. This was the case with the previously mentioned USC Professor George J. Sanchez, a FGCS and a first-generation immigrant, who is able to empathize with many FGCS and underrepresented minority students at USC. Without these kinds of faculty getting involved with diversifying campus programming, universities risk losing out on discovering some of the brightest and most motivated students.

FGCS are Ideal Candidates for Study Abroad Programs

When interviewing these students, I made note of how they talked about their intentions for studying abroad and traveling. It soon occurred to me that these students are capable of being outstanding global ambassadors and citizens. Students such as Brandon, Angela, and Tricia treated the idea of studying abroad as a way to gain global awareness and insight so that they could increase their cultural competence. For Brandon, it was a goal for him to visit a culture similar but different from his Mexican background, which is why he chose the Philippines. He states that the Philippines had infrastructure and a language similar to what he already knows and, like Mexico, contained multiple subcultures to explore. He traveled quite a lot during his semester at UP Dilman; he went from Manila to Cebu as well as to regions where they spoke

Chavacano (Spanish-based creole; he did not understand this language too well). He took public transportation anywhere and everywhere that piqued his interest; he even recalls taking a random bus to the end of its route and being taken in by the bus driver's family until he was able to return home. Locals treated him like one of their own and offered food, shelter, and hospitality with no hesitation. Brandon stated that these kinds of experiences are not part of the general format of study abroad programs and they take extra effort and motivation to engage in.

Brandon's experience in the Philippines made me reflect on my own experiences when I was anticipating studying abroad in Wales. I knew this was going to be a different travel experience than those I am used to, so I made an effort to understand as much as I could about Welsh culture. I had made an effort to acquaint myself with the Welsh language, cuisine, politics, history, and modern culture. I wanted to be adequately informed when I arrived to ensure that I was sensitive to the local culture and life. Angela had a similar mentality as myself when preparing for her upcoming trip to Bali as she was inspired by her limited travel experience to actively learn how to be more respectful and appreciative while abroad. Her travel experience is more extensive now that she has traveled abroad with family and for work, but her intentions remain pure. She plans to visit local shops, attend cooking classes for local cuisine, visit temples, and appreciate the environment. Her hope is that she comes home with internal changes that reflect a culturally competent person.

Some students had prior experience with their own culture that enabled them to conduct themselves in a respectful and sensitive manner while abroad. Similar to Brandon, Tricia comes from a similar background in that she is also a first-generation immigrant whose parents are from Mexico. They each understand what it is like to have their culture disrespected and undermined, so they try to avoid doing the same to others. Tricia, who invested a lot of time in learning about

Korean culture and the language before she studied there, states that, “If someone were to come from Korea to Mexico or the States and was with me, I would like for them to come with an enthusiasm of appreciating a new culture. So that’s the mentality I came with.” Brandon came to view the term “foreigner” as being a sort of insult, and more comparable to the term “outsider”, because it was weaponized against him despite him being born in the U.S. He soon realized that this term meant something different to him during his trip to the Philippines since he was treated like an actual foreigner, someone who was there to explore and experience a new culture. Each of these students took the proper time and effort to get acquainted with the culture of the country they would be visiting. Brandon and I wondered if this were something that CGCS often think of when they plan to study abroad, however, Tricia gave some insight as to why she does not believe that this is always the case. While in South Korea, she met a student who had parents who went to college, an aunt and step-sibling who studied abroad, a trust fund, and who was staying in South Korea for an entire academic year. This particular student stood out to Tricia because she noticed how they were consistently upset about not being spoken to in English. Tricia stated that “That’s not how the world works....If you wanted to speak English, stick with your own country or go to an English speaking country.” which is a statement that I could not agree with more.

However, I do want to make a disclaimer since I understand that this can come off like I am being condescending to CGCS. These students and I understand that CGCS are more than capable of being culturally sensitive because it all comes down to our upbringing. This is an observation about how FGCS typically view study abroad and their experiences with how CGCS treat studying abroad. With FGCS being a very diverse group, it is no surprise to me that they prioritize productively engaging in different cultures and experiences abroad no matter how

unfamiliar. Rausch (2017) introduces the idea of First-Generation Strength, a theory which states that because FGCS have been able to pursue activities and endeavors that their families have not been able to pursue, they developed strengths and experiences that enable them to navigate and overcome various obstacles. I think that this theory aligns with every student I was able to talk to as well as with myself.

Conclusion

The history of study abroad is a complicated one, and there is still a severe lack of diversity within the study abroad community at a national level. Higher education institutions have a responsibility to all students to encourage their involvement in collegiate level activities and programs as well as to create an inclusive environment that addresses unique and universal student concerns. As seen throughout this paper, there are a variety of circumstances that inhibit FGCS from getting involved with campus life and programs that would benefit them professionally, socially, and personally to be part of. Ultimately, it is up to FGCS and their respective universities to learn how to engage with one another in a way that benefits them both. Moreover, it is the faculty and professors who work directly with FGCS on a daily basis who have more influence over their academic, social, and personal lives than they might realize. The experiences that FGCS had with faculty that are highlighted in this project are not to be taken lightly. These student experiences are not isolated or rare occurrences, and there are implications for how faculty and staff should approach complicated issues with FGCS all of which point to the need for increased compassionate care on campus. It is not difficult to notice the stark differences in the responses of FGCS who received proper support versus those who were denied such support. Engaging with students and their personal lives, concerns, aspirations, and professional goals (within reason of course) will allow educators to learn more about the

demographics of their respective campuses. With that being said, I believe that it is in CSUF's best interest to know who is likely to be a FGCS and which students on campus are FGCS. This information will inform which kinds of programs, CSUF and other higher education institutions, seek to implement as well as how they attempt to increase student involvement in those programs. It will also inevitably diversify the programs already on campus and inspire others, such as those specific to FGCS and other underrepresented minority students. As it pertains to increasing FGCS involvement in the study abroad community, from what was already mentioned in this project, it seems that finances and graduation delay are amongst the most common concerns that FGCS have. This is immediately followed up by concerns that parents of FGCS have about their child going abroad when it is not commonplace for them to do so. Programs that pay special attention to these concerns will encourage FGCS to involve themselves in international endeavors, as seen with the Planning Scholars, Gilman Scholarship, and Norman Topping Scholars programs.

Aside from wanting to spread awareness to both higher education institutions, students, and the general public about FGCS experiences that take place on and off campus, I also wanted to encourage higher education institutions to recognize their FGCS population and acknowledge their achievements. The goal of this project is not to dwell on the disadvantages that FGCS may have when they go through college. The students I talked to give me no reason to view them in any other way than the strong and capable individuals they are. These students have been able to inspire their own families and friends to seek out international opportunities, something that would not have been possible if it were not for their valued involvement in the study abroad program. For instance, Brandon states that, "As soon as I broke that barrier, it convinced all my uncles, my aunts, my own parents that it's not so scary to travel and to let your kids travel." As

for Tricia, her involvement in the study abroad community led her to inspiring other members of “Hermanas Unidas”, a group on campus dedicated to promoting the academic and professional success of Latina/Chicana students, to seek out international opportunities like study abroad. She has also aided her sister, who is in high school, in preparing to study abroad this summer by helping her with the application process and prepping her to live abroad. It is important for me and these students to view FGCS as motivated, curious, and proud individuals. Despite the need to recognize their struggles in navigating higher education, this information should be utilized in a way that ultimately uses their experiences to inform future actions.

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